

THE ARCHITECTURE OF HISTORICAL MONUMENTS OF KARMANA CITY

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Abstract. *The article aims to consider the architecture of historical monuments of Karmana city. Karmana is known in Uzbekistan as one of the oldest regions located at the intersection of the Ancient East and West, in the lower reaches of the Zarafshan River. The age of this area can be judged by the unique traces discovered in Uchtut and Sarmyshsay, found there on more than 400 monuments of archeology, architecture and art.*

Keywords: *Karmana city, monument, archeology, architecture, history, workshop, petroglyph.*

We know that Navoi, as a region, is relatively young, but without any doubt it can be said that it has a long history and ancient roots. This is evidenced by the ancient city of Karmana, the Nurata region, the sacred architectural monuments of Kasym Sheikh, Arif Diggaroni, Raboti Malik, Toshmaszhit, Kugumbaz Karmana is known in Uzbekistan as one of the most ancient regions located at the intersection of the Ancient East and West, in the lower reaches of the Zarafshan River. The age of this area can be judged by the unique traces discovered in Uchtut and Sarmyshsay, found there on more than 400 monuments of archeology, architecture and art. Some of them are of interest to historians around the world. For example, a workshop for the manufacture of stone tools, indicating the residence of primitive people here from the Middle Paleolithic era, and their settlement, the remains of found mines of the Neolithic era, as well as petroglyphs - petroglyphs carved by hunters and pastoralists as early as the beginning of the Bronze Age, as well as medieval water mills. Karmana is known not only for its historical values, but also deserves attention as the abode of scientists. In the IX-XII centuries. sciences such as logic, theology, hadith studies flourished here, dictionaries were compiled.

Many scientists have made a great contribution to the development of both religious and secular sciences. The central attraction of Karmana is the architectural ensemble on the southern outskirts of the city, the Kasym-Sheikh Complex. The complex owes its appearance to a real historical figure. He was a local native, popular in Central Asia, religious and political figure Kasym-sheikh Azizan Karminagi (1500/1578-79), head of the Sufi brotherhood of Yassavia. The architectural ensemble includes three main buildings: khonako and two khazirs ("enclosed place", "fence") – one of the types of open-air funerary building. The earliest building is Khazir Kasim-sheikh. According to contemporaries, the building was built by the Sufi himself and could serve as a madrasah until his death. In the work of Abu Tahirkhuzha Samarkandi "Samaria" some information about Mir Said Bakhrom is given. He enjoyed well-deserved respect and influence among the people due to his knowledge, intelligence and ability to work miracles. The mausoleum of Mir Said Bakhrom, located in the center of Karmana, was erected in the 10th-11th centuries. and is a national monument. The structure was erected from 102 bricks, in the form of a quadrangular shape with one dome. The building was restored several times, as a result of which the original appearance was lost. 30 kilometers west of the city of Karman, near the village of

Hazora, one of the oldest mosques in Maverannahr, the Deggaron Mosque, has been preserved. It was erected no later than the beginning of the 11th century. On the left bank of the Zarafshan River, on the territory of a once prosperous small village. The inhabitants of the village were engaged in the manufacture of high-quality boilers. It is noteworthy that one of the famous representatives of the Sufi school Khozhagon Sheikh Mavlono Orif Deggaroniy (1313-1376) was born and was buried in this village.

He is considered one of the mentors of the largest representative of the Khozhagon school, Bokhauddin Nakshband. The mosque was built in a mixed technique: floors, columns and partly the foundation - from burnt bricks, walls from mud bricks and pakhsa blocks. The soffits of the arches carrying the central dome are decorated with original moldings of brick and ganch, forming a trefoil in cross section. Small sphero-conical domes over square compartments have a transitional tier of cantilever-cellular sails. The mosque has been restored. In the new, rebuilt museum building, expositions of objects found on this land are presented. One of the sheikhs who lived in Karman in the XIV century. and who were like-minded Mavlono Orif Deggaroniy and Khoja Bahauddin Nakshbandi, was Khoja Khusrav. As a well-known scientist, one of the propagandists of the Nakshbandi tariqa, he fought against heresy and khurofat (superstition). Some historical information and legends about the life, work and supernatural miraculous power of Khoja Khusrav are given in the book "Bahouddin balogardon" by Abdullah Musin Muhammad Bokir ibn Muhammad Ali. Currently, the tomb of Khoja Khusrav has been restored anew and turned into a well-maintained memorial complex. The years of independence of Uzbekistan have become a time in which due attention was paid to the historical heritage of the country. And among the many monuments of antiquity, these buildings are evidence of the dawn of Maverannahr. Admiring with their beauty, the sights of Karmana today are of historical, spiritual value and testify to the great power of the creative art of the ancient architects who lived on this land.

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